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“MEMORIES NEVER GONE”

My niece, who is closed to me, passed away in a tragic way, even though she brought to the hospital and all the Doctors made all the help to save her life, but they cannot make it anymore. She was revived in 10 times pump. The result of her diagnosis was already complicated: pneumonia, kidney and heart failure. I have been crying every minute, every time I will remember her. I always see her face in my mind.

I cannot take that she left and never come back. It really hurts me and Family. I will never forget all her goodness and everything she done. Her reminiscence has been together will never fade away.

Lastly, all I can say, God has plans each of one of us.